

Medicinal Plants Administered for Inoculation against Seasonal and Infectious Diseases: A Health Promotion Approach

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Prior to the emergence of contemporary vaccination methods, traditional societies used their culturally established practices to avert infectious diseases. This paper presents the findings of a qualitative medical ethnobotanical investigation carried out in four districts of Limpopo Province, South Africa. The study findings identify six indigenous medicinal plants utilised as medicinal sources to enhance disease resistance. Decoctions and infusions are administered orally to limit susceptibility to infections and reduce their severity. Further scientific research on the therapeutic plants found in the study is recommended to evaluate their efficacy and safety. Understanding these inoculation protocols could be shared to strengthen community resilience against diseases and pandemics.

Keywords: Infectious diseases, preventive medicine, medicinal plants, indigenous vaccines

Vaccination denotes the administration of a vaccine (an antigen) to stimulate an individual's immune system to develop adaptive (acquired) immunity to a pathogen (Frazzoli et al., 2023). The terms vaccination, inoculation, and immunisation are often used interchangeably to describe the artificial induction of immunity against various infectious diseases. A vaccine, therefore, is a biological preparation that provides active acquired immunity to a specific disease (Mehari, 2021). The immunity gained through vaccination helps eradicate and reduce diseases such as polio, measles, diphtheria, and tetanus (Taaffe et al., 2024). Before the advent of modern vaccination techniques, traditional societies worldwide had employed their culturally developed strategies to prevent infectious diseases and mitigate significant harm to their communities. Mehari (2021) asserts that traditional inoculation has been used globally for over 80 years to limit mortality and disability caused by different diseases. Rankoana (2023) acknowledges that local communities employ diverse traditional inoculation procedures to avert the transmission of contagious diseases. These methods, which utilise the inherent powers of microorganisms, are sometimes perceived as ancient or traditional biotechnology (Mehari, 2021). Alum (2024) adds that the utilisation of indigenous plant-based remedies is essential in indigenous healthcare methods. This type of knowledge is a crucial attribute passed down through generations, including various healthcare applications, for therapeutic, preventive, and protective care.

However, the present paper describes the indigenous inoculation methods and practices used to prevent disease attacks, as reported by participants from four communities in Limpopo Province, South

Africa. The study aligns with the World Health Organisation's goal to enhance equitable access to safe, quality, and effective health care services that meet communities' needs and build sustainable and culturally sensitive primary health care (WHO, 2019). This goal is supported by the Declaration of Astana's Global Conference on Primary Health Care in October 2018, which states that the success of primary health care is driven by applying scientific as well as traditional knowledge and extending access to a range of healthcare services, which include traditional medicines (WHO, 2019).

Method

Study Location

This study investigated the use of medicinal plants by members of rural communities to prepare medicines specifically aimed at limiting susceptibility to infections and seasonal diseases. Participants comprised four groups of Bapedi people residing in the Capricorn, Mopani, Sekhukhune, and Waterberg district municipalities of Limpopo Province, South Africa. The province covers 125,755 square kilometers, making up 10.3% of South Africa's total geographical area and ranking as the fifth largest province (Statistics, South Africa, 2021). The study settings were selected for their rural contexts. The selected communities demonstrate economic, religious, social, and political connections, highlighting the province's rich cultural heritage (Limpopo Development Plan, 2015-2019).

Study Design

A qualitative study was conducted to gather data on indigenous medicinal plants used in the preparation of preventive medicine against infections and seasonal diseases. The participants consisted of 160 members from four communities, with forty members selected from each community. The sample included 80 men and 80 women aged over 30 years.

Measure

A series of semi-structured, face-to-face interviews were conducted in the participants' households to collect data on infectious and seasonal diseases, preventive measures, and the indigenous plants used to produce inoculation medicine at the household level. Each

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interview lasted for one hour. Language specialists assisted the researcher in translating the interview guide into Sepedi. The interviews were conducted in Sepedi, the participants' native language, and were audio recorded.

Statistical Analysis

The data were processed through thematic content analysis. All

audio recordings of the interviews were transcribed verbatim, translated into English, and edited by a language expert. The data classification presented in Table 1 below presents themes and sub-themes, including infectious diseases, seasonal diseases, and the indigenous plant species used to make preventive medicines.

Results and Discussion

Table 1

Medicinal Plants Used in Disease Inoculation

Seasonal diseases	Infectious diseases	Inoculation method	Indigenous plant-derived medicines
Cough	Cough	Oral administration of root decoction	<i>Amaranthus hybridus</i> L. (Sebjane)
Cough	Cough	Oral administration of root decoction	<i>Artemisia affra.</i> (Lengana)
Flu	Flu	and leaf infusion	
Whooping cough	Whooping cough		
Measles	Measles		
Smallpox	Smallpox		
Measles	Measles	Oral administration of the root	<i>Berchemia discolor</i> (Klotzsch
Smallpox	Smallpox		Hemsl.) (Malaka)
Cough	Cough	Oral administration of root decoction	<i>Drimia robusta</i> Bak
Flu	Flu	and leaf infusion	
Whooping cough	Whooping cough	Oral administration of leaf infusion	<i>Lippia javanica</i>
Cough	Cough	decoction and leaf	
Flu	Flu		
Whooping cough	Whooping cough		
Cough	Cough	Oral administration of a decoction	<i>Siphnochilus aethiopicus</i> (Schweif)
Flu	Flu	of bulb chips	B.L. Burt (Serokolo)
Whooping cough	Whooping cough	Bulb chips	

Table 1 presents six native plant species, whose leaves, roots, and bulbs are sources of preventive medicine used to inoculate against seasonal and infectious diseases. The medicines enhance the immune system by reducing susceptibility and severity to seasonal and infectious diseases. Participants aged over 45 successfully recognised all six plant species, likely due to their greater familiarity with medicinal plants within their environment. Participants have identified that seasonal diseases are also infectious (Table 1). Consequently, participants recognise and utilise medicinal plants to address seasonal and infectious diseases. The frequently utilised plant materials include the root, leaf, and bulb. Participants utilise these botanical substances to create decoctions and infusions that enhance immunity and guard against seasonal and infectious ailments. Cordero et al. (2022) support these findings by demonstrating that the root and leaf plant materials are widely recognised and commonly used as sources of medicine administered to limit vulnerability to infectious and seasonal illnesses.

Inoculation against Seasonal Diseases

Participants (98%) reported that some diseases that affect community members are seasonal. Participants reported having encountered these diseases during certain seasons of the year. For instance, they indicated that during winter, several people become vulnerable to seasonal illnesses such as influenza, cough, pertussis, and measles. The probability and intensity of these seasonal diseases are mitigated by vaccination with native plant-based remedies

(Table 1). Seasonal human infections encompass childhood illnesses, including measles, diphtheria, and chickenpox, as well as faecaloral infections like cholera and rotavirus, and vector-borne diseases (Cordero et al., 2020; Kshirsagar & Rao, 2021).

Knowledge about these seasonal diseases helps in reducing the probability of infections and alleviating their severity through vaccination. In contrast to other disease prevention measures recommended and implemented by the mainstream health practitioners, inoculation with indigenous plant-derived remedies constitutes a form of self-medication, which is the first line of offering primary health care at the household level. The indigenous inoculation practices reported in Table 1 align with the study of Helman (2000) and Taaffe et al. (2024) which acknowledge that traditional medicine is formulated for immunization against disease using decoctions and infusions to prevent disease. Lawal et al. (2020) assert that the use of indigenous medicinal herbs to combat infections is an established practice, including its use in endeavours to prevent COVID-19 infections. Goldin et al. (2024) recognise the efficacy of traditional medicine uses in seasonal influenza vaccination to reduce the severity of the disease and fatality rates.

Inoculation against Infectious

Participants reported using indigenous plant-derived medicines to limit the attack and proliferation of infections, including influenza, cough, smallpox, and measles. A significant majority of participants (85%) indicated their use of biomedical vaccines to mitigate the

transmission and severity of diseases, notwithstanding their knowledge of indigenous botanicals that could similarly reduce the spread and susceptibility to infections. A minority of participants (15%) indicated the use of indigenous preventative strategies alongside biological vaccines to mitigate the transmission of illnesses. The use of traditional medicine derived from indigenous flora to avert infections aligns with evidence indicating that these plants play a crucial role in fortifying communities against infectious diseases during outbreaks and pandemics. Frazzoli et al. (2023) concede that African herbal treatments encompass micronutrients and bioactive substances. These chemicals may enhance the immune system. The efficacy of conventional vaccination techniques utilising medicinal plants is corroborated by COVID-19 data, which demonstrates that the application of these phytotherapeutics to enhance immunity led to fewer than one million fatalities in Africa, rendering it the region with the lowest mortality rate during the COVID-19 pandemic (WHO, 2019; 2021).

Conclusion

In their cosmology, local communities are aware of seasonal diseases and the strategies to mitigate their vulnerability and severity. Preventive measures against infections generally encompass medical ethnobotanical knowledge that has developed alongside human culture. This knowledge is shown in the present study about the indigenous plant species that are sources of preventive medicine used to inoculate against seasonal and infectious diseases. Susceptibility to infectious and seasonal diseases is limited by oral administration of decoctions and infusions. The primary finding of the study is that seasonal diseases are contagious. The therapeutic application of medicinal plants for immunization against infections and seasonal diseases is rooted in indigenous healthcare knowledge that has been passed down through generations. Additional scientific investigations into the therapeutic plants identified in the study are advised to assess their efficacy and safety, protect the species, and preserve the knowledge of their utilisation as the intellectual property of the studied communities. Knowledge of these inoculation procedures could be disseminated to enhance community resilience against epidemics and pandemics.

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